

ORGANIZATION OF RESCUE AND OTHER URGENT WORK IN RAILWAY TRANSPORT IN THE EVENT OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Annotation: This article addresses the issue rescue and other urgent work in emergency situations is one of the main tasks of state policy in the field of ensuring the safety of the population. The purpose of rescue operations is to save people and provide medical assistance to the injured, eliminate accidents. The process of rescue and other urgent work, which also conducts the priority life support of the population, the distribution of funds received in the form of assistance to the population located in the emergency zone and evacuated from it, is considered.

Keywords: Rescue and other urgent work in emergency situations, the conduct and improper organization of the SIDNR, the forces and means of the State Emergency Service.

Rescue and other urgent work in emergency situations is one of the main tasks of state policy in the field of ensuring the safety of the population. The purpose of rescue operations is to save people and provide medical assistance to the victims, eliminate accidents [1].

In the modern world with its high level of technical development, humanity has not only learned to avoid disasters by inventing more and more new means of protection from negative factors, but also received a new type of emergency because of this - man-made. Even 100-200 years ago, earthquakes, floods, tsunamis, tornadoes, etc., ranked first among emergencies in terms of damage caused, but now the very nature of emergencies has changed.

Along with the nature of emergencies, the method of their liquidation and rescue operations has also changed. With technological progress, disasters such as plane crashes, accidents at radiation hazardous facilities, and the consequences of the use of potent toxic substances came to the world. At the same time, natural emergencies still claim human lives, which in most cases is the result of improper organization of rescue operations. Often, people die because of the wrong conduct and wrong organization of the SIDNR, so it is necessary to understand the basics, the scope of rescue operations [2].

Urgent work during emergency response- activities for the comprehensive provision of rescue operations, the provision of medical and other types of assistance to the population affected in emergency situations, the creation of the conditions necessary to preserve the life and health of people, and maintain their efficiency.

rescue work- actions in the emergency zone to save people, material and cultural values, protect the environment, localize it and suppress or bring to the minimum possible level the impact of the typical day of its dangerous factors.

Rescue operations include: activities related to the search for victims, their extraction from rubble, damaged vehicles, burning buildings, evacuation (removal, withdrawal, removal) of people from the emergency zone, provision of first medical and other types of assistance to victims [3].

Urgent work includes: localization and extinguishing fires, strengthening the structures of structures that threaten to collapse, restoring energy and communication networks, communication lines, roads and facilities for rescue operations, removal of material assets, etc.

Other urgent work- this is an activity for the comprehensive provision of emergency rescue operations, the provision of medical and other types of assistance to the population affected in emergency situations, the creation of conditions that are minimally necessary to preserve the life and health of people, and maintain their efficiency.

Figure 1. Intelligence in the emergency zone

The success of carrying out measures to eliminate emergency situations, the implementation of emergency rescue is achieved:

advance purposeful preparation of command and control bodies, forces and means of the State Emergency Service for actions in the event of a threat and an emergency situation; emergency response of the State Emergency Service to the occurrence of an emergency, organizing effective reconnaissance, alerting command and control agencies, forces and means, their timely advancement to the emergency zone, deploying a command and control system, the necessary forces and means;

making an informed decision to eliminate the emergency [8].

situation and its consistent implementation; continuous, firm and sustainable work management (their planning, coordination, control) and close interaction of participants in

the course of work; continuous rescue and other emergency operations day and night, in any weather until they are fully completed, using methods and technologies that ensure the fullest use of the capabilities of emergency rescue teams; the steady implementation by the participants of the work of the established modes of operation and security measures, the timely change of formations in order to restore their performance; organization of uninterrupted and comprehensive logistics of work, life support of the population and participants in the work, providing them with psychological assistance.

Figure 2. Grouping of rescue units

Advance preparation in the country for the elimination of possible emergency situations is organized and carried out by central and local executive bodies in accordance with their powers established by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of relevant programs and plans.

The main early measures that ensure the creation of effective prerequisites for the successful elimination of emergencies in the future are:

- training of officials, governing bodies, formations and population to act in emergency situations;
- creation of groupings of forces aimed at protected territories;
- carrying out the necessary technical equipment of the governing bodies and forces of the State Emergency Service;
- maintaining readiness of command and control bodies, forces and means of the State Emergency Service;
- creation of reserves of material resources for the elimination of emergency situations;
- planning possible actions to eliminate emergency situations, organization of interaction between subsystems and links of the State Emergency Service;
- constant monitoring of the situation in the republic, related to emergencies.

Emergencies due to their diversity require for each of their types the appropriate organizational forms, methods and technologies for emergency rescue and other urgent work, which, in turn, are also diverse and numerous.

At the same time, the rescue business is constantly developing, specializing, following the path of division of labor, introducing into practice new, more advanced methods, technologies, technical equipment, including those specific to each type of work. In this regard, in order to objectively and in detail judge the content of rescue and other urgent work, it is necessary to consider them in relation to specific types of emergency situations.

Rescue and other urgent work can be presented in the form of a number of sets of measures:

- informational and analytical nature, including the identification and assessment of the danger that has arisen, and informing about it;
- localization and (or) suppression of lesions, termination exposure to primary damaging factors, if possible;
- saving people, providing them with the necessary assistance, first of all medical; exclusion of occurrence secondary damaging factors on objects of secondary danger;
- protection and rescue of material and cultural values;
- restoration of the minimum necessary life support for the population.

Considering the composition of typical complexes of rescue measures, it should be borne in mind that they also include a significant part of the measures to protect the population and territories [4].

In a generalized form, rescue and other urgent work includes the following operational activities:

detection in the process of monitoring or by other means of the fact of the occurrence of a natural disaster, accident, natural or man-made disaster;

timely notification of local executive bodies, territorial divisions of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, management bodies of the State Emergency Service and the population about the occurrence of an emergency;

conducting reconnaissance in the lesions and the emergency zone,

assessment of the situation and forecasting its development;

establishment of an access regime to the emergency zone, security public order in it;

providing the population with personal protective equipment;

shelter of the population and personnel in protective structures, organization

use of personal protective equipment;

search and rescue of the victims, their extraction from the rubble, removal from lesions;

providing victims with first medical, pre-medical and first aid medical assistance, their evacuation to medical institutions;

Figure 3. Providing medical assistance to victims

sanitization of the population, personnel, liquidation participants emergency; localization and (or) suppression of primary and secondary foci [5].
damage, neutralization of sources of secondary danger; evacuation of the population from the emergency zone;
demolition of rubble, clearing and equipping of traffic routes in the area emergency; disinfection, decontamination of territories, buildings, structures, equipment, transport, property, means of protection;
construction of temporary and strengthening of existing hydraulic and other protective structures;
carrying out urgent emergency and restoration work on systems life support and life;
registration, identification and burial of the dead;
conducting sanitary and hygienic anti-epidemic events;
implementation of measures to protect farm animals and plants, veterinary and preventive measures; information and advisory services to citizens in connection with emergency.
In the process of rescue and other urgent work, the priority life support of the population is also carried out, the distribution of funds received in the form of assistance to the population located in the emergency zone and evacuated from it [3].
The fact of the onset of a natural disaster, accident, natural or man-made disaster can be detected by monitoring institutions, on-duty dispatch services of potentially hazardous facilities, automated means (systems) for monitoring and controlling hazardous factors, and outside observers from among the population. If there is a forecast of the occurrence of an emergency, the fixation of the occurrence of the source of the emergency, as a rule, occurs earlier than without it.
Information about an event that has occurred or is predicted by means of communication is sent to local executive bodies, territorial divisions of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to the management bodies of the State Emergency Service, where a decision is made to notify the population and collect an emergency commission.
The population is alerted and informed about an emergency situation by using centralized alert systems operating in the relevant territory and (or) local alert systems created at potentially hazardous facilities.

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